

Magic Number Theory of Superconducting Proximity Effects and Wigner Delay Times in Graphene-Like Molecules

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

1. Calculation of Wigner delay times for on-resonance transport

In the absence of external gating, electron transport through molecules under ambient conditions is usually off-resonance. On the other hand, if a molecule is gated such that the energy E of electrons passing through the molecule is close to an energy level of the molecule, then in principle transport could be on resonance. To illustrate the properties of τ_{ab} in this limit, we now examine a number of examples, under the condition that the scatterer is weakly coupled to the leads, such that $\frac{\gamma_a}{\gamma} \ll 1$ and $\frac{\gamma_b}{\gamma} \ll 1$.

Example 1

In the limit $\beta \ll \alpha$, equation (14) of the main text reduces to

$$\tau_{ab} \approx - \left[\frac{\dot{\alpha} \sin k}{(1 + \alpha \cos k)^2 + (\alpha \sin k)^2} \right] \quad (1)$$

Example 1a. As an example, consider the case where

$$g_{ab} \approx \frac{\psi_a \psi_b}{E - \lambda_0} \quad (2)$$

In this case, $\beta = 0$ and

$$\tau_{ab} \approx \left[\frac{\Gamma_{ab}}{(E - \lambda_{ab})^2 + \Gamma_{ab}^2} \right] \quad (3)$$

In this expression, $\lambda_{ab} = \lambda_0 - \sigma$, $\sigma = \sigma_a + \sigma_b$ and $\Gamma_{ab} = \Gamma_a + \Gamma_b$, where $\sigma_a = -\frac{\gamma_a^2}{\gamma} \psi_a^2 \cos k$ and $\Gamma_a = \frac{\gamma_a^2}{\gamma} \psi_a^2 \sin k$ and similarly for σ_b, Γ_b . Hence on resonance, where $E = \lambda_{ab}$, the delay time reduces to $\tau_{ab} \approx 1/\Gamma_{ab}$. On the other hand, if transport is off resonance and E lies close to the gap centre,

$\tau_{ab} \approx \frac{\Gamma_{ab}}{\delta^2}$, where δ is half the HOMO-LUMO gap. Since $\Gamma_{ab} \ll \delta$, this demonstrates that the ‘on-resonance’ delay time is much longer than the ‘off-resonance’ delay time.

Interestingly, the transmission coefficient $T_{ab}(E) = |t_{ab}|^2$ in this case is given by the Breit-Wigner formula:

$$T_{ab} \approx \left[\frac{4\Gamma_a \Gamma_b}{(E - \lambda_{ab})^2 + \Gamma_{ab}^2} \right] \quad (4)$$

Hence the delay time is related to the electrical conductance by

$$T_{ab}/\tau_{ab} \approx \frac{4\Gamma_a\Gamma_b}{\Gamma_a + \Gamma_b} \quad (5)$$

Example 1b

As a further example, consider the case of a Fano resonance created by a pendant orbital of energy ϵ coupled to ψ by a coupling constant η , such that $\lambda_0 = \lambda_1 + \eta^2/(E - \epsilon)$. In this case, since λ_0 is energy dependent, one obtains

$$\tau_{ab} \approx \frac{\Gamma_{ab} \left(1 + \frac{\eta^2}{(E - \epsilon)^2}\right)}{\left(E - \lambda_{ab} - \frac{\eta^2}{(E - \epsilon)^2}\right)^2 + \Gamma_{ab}^2} \quad (6)$$

Near the Fano resonance, where $E \approx \epsilon$, this yields

$$\tau_{ab} \approx \frac{\Gamma_{ab}}{\eta^2} \quad (7)$$

For $\eta \ll \Gamma_{ab}$, this yields $\tau_{ab} \gg 1/\Gamma_{ab}$, which means that the electron spends a long time on the pendant orbital.

In this case,

$$T_{ab}/\tau_{ab} \approx \frac{4\Gamma_a\Gamma_b}{(\Gamma_a + \Gamma_b) \left(1 + \frac{\eta^2}{(E - \epsilon)^2}\right)} \quad (8)$$

which reflects the fact that T_{ab} vanishes at the Fano resonance, where $E = \epsilon$.

2. Derivation of equations (4) and (6) of the main text.

As discussed in [1], the low-bias, low-temperature electrical conductance σ of a molecule connected to normal-metal electrode and one or more superconducting electrodes is given by

$$\sigma = \frac{4e^2}{h} R_a. \quad (9)$$

Here R_a is the Andreev reflection coefficient describing the probability that an electron from the normal electrode traverses the molecule, Andreev reflects as a hole and then exits through the normal electrode. This process is accompanied by a Cooper pair entering the superconducting electrode and therefore carries a current. The electrons and holes of such a structure are described by the Bogoliubov de Gennes Hamiltonian

$$H = \begin{pmatrix} h & \Delta e^{i\phi} \\ \Delta e^{-i\phi} & -h \end{pmatrix}. \quad (10)$$

In this equation, $\Delta e^{i\phi}$ is the superconducting order parameter, with uniform phase ϕ , which is non-zero in the superconducting electrode only and provides the coupling between electrons and holes. Conceptually, this doubling of the Hamiltonian, means that the pi system of the central core should be views as comprising both electronic and hole degrees of freedom, as shown in the figure below

In the absence of the electrodes, the mid-gap Greens function of the electronic system is $g^e = -h^{-1}$, whereas the Green's function of the hole system is $g^h = h^{-1}$. When the superconductor is weakly attached, the Green's function matrix element connecting the electronic pi orbital at i to the hole pi orbital at i is, to lowest order in the coupling, $G_{ii} = g_{ij}^h \Delta e^{-i\phi} g_{ji}^e = -(g_{ij}^e)^2 \Delta e^{-i\phi}$, where $\Delta e^{-i\phi}$ is the coupling between particles and holes mediated by the superconductor. Hence $R_a \sim |G_{ii}|^2 \sim (g_{ij}^e)^4 \sim (M_{ij})^4$

Similarly, if the molecule is weakly connected to two superconductors with order parameter phases ϕ_L and ϕ_R via pi orbitals m and p , and to a normal electrode via pi orbital l ,

$$G_{ll} = g_{lm}^e \Delta e^{-i\phi_L} g_{ml}^h + g_{lp}^h \Delta e^{-i\phi_R} g_{pl}^h = -\Delta [(g_{lm}^e)^2 e^{-i\phi_L} + (g_{lp}^h)^2 e^{-i\phi_R}]. \quad (11)$$

Hence

$$R_a \sim |G_{ii}|^2 \sim |(g_{lm}^e)^2 e^{-i\phi_L} + (g_{lp}^h)^2 e^{-i\phi_R}|^2 \sim |(M_{lm})^2 e^{-i\phi_L} + (M_{lp})^2 e^{-i\phi_R}|^2 \quad (12)$$

3. Derivation of equation (5) of the main text

According to Ref. [2], at zero temperature the critical current through a phase biased Josephson junction flowing through lead R (see Figure 4 in the main text) can be calculated by:

$$I_c^{(ij)} = \max_{\phi_L - \phi_R} \left(\frac{2}{\pi} \text{Im} \int_{-\infty}^0 dE \text{Tr} \left(G_{MR}^{(ij)} \hat{I}_{MR} \right) \right). \quad (13)$$

Here $G_{MR}^{(ij)}$ and $\hat{I}_{MR}$ are the retarded Green's function matrix element and the current operator between lead R and the central molecule M. Labels (ij) in this notation means, that the left superconducting lead with superconducting order parameter $\Delta_L e^{i\phi_L}$ is connected to site i of the molecule and right superconducting lead with order parameter $\Delta_R e^{i\phi_R}$ to site j . The current operator is given by the coupling Hamiltonian between the molecule and the right lead, thus it is proportional to the coupling strength γ_c . (For the meaning of γ_c see Figure 4 of the main text)

The element $G_{MR}^{(ij)}$ of the Green's function matrix $G^{(ij)}$ can be calculated via the Dyson equation

$$G^{(ij)} = (G_0^{-1} - V^{(ij)})^{-1}, \quad (14)$$

where $G_0 = \text{diag}(G_L, G_M, G_R)$ is the Green's function of the detached system containing of the isolated central molecule (G_M) and the two unattached leads (G_L and G_R), and $V^{(ij)}$ is the coupling between the leads and the central molecule. Since the magic number theory is a weak coupling theory, we may consider $V^{(ij)}$ as a perturbation and expand the Dyson equation into series:

$$G^{(ij)} = G_0 + G_0 V^{(ij)} G_0 + G_0 V^{(ij)} G_0 V^{(ij)} G_0 + G_0 V^{(ij)} G_0 V^{(ij)} G_0 V^{(ij)} G_0 + \dots \quad (15)$$

It can be shown by straightforward calculations that the first non-vanishing contribution to the Josephson current comes from the third order term in the expansion series of the Green's function. In particular, the critical current can be given by the expression

$$I_c^{(ij)} \cong \max_{\phi_L - \phi_R} \left(\frac{2\gamma_c^4}{\pi} \text{Im} \int_{-\infty}^0 dE (g_{ij}^e)^2 \text{Tr}(G_L \tau_3 G_R) \right). \quad (16)$$

In the derivation of Eq. (16) we also took advantage of the block-diagonal structure of the Green's function of the central molecule, namely $G_M = \text{diag}(g^e, g^h) = \tau_3 \otimes g^e$, where τ_3 is the third Pauli matrix.

Usually the main contribution to the critical current originates from the Andreev bound states with energy located within the superconducting gap ($0 > E > -\Delta$). In this energy regime the Green's function of the central molecule can be considered to be energy independent, and the above expression can be further simplified to:

$$I_c^{(ij)} \cong \frac{2\gamma_c^4}{\pi} (g_{ij}^e)^2 \max_{\phi_L - \phi_R} \left(\text{Im} \int_{-\Delta}^0 dE \text{Tr}(G_L \tau_3 G_R) \right). \quad (17)$$

Hence, we arrive at $I_c^{(ij)} \sim (g_{ij}^e)^2 \sim (M_{ij})^2$ that coincides with Eq. (5) in the main text.

[1] C. J. Lambert, R. Raimondi, Phase-coherent Transport in Hybrid Superconducting Nanostructures. *J. Phys.: Condensed Matter* **1998**, *10*, 901-941.

[2] P. Rakyta, A. Kormányos, J. Cserti, Magnetic Field Oscillations of the Critical Current in Long Ballistic Graphene Josephson Junctions. *Phys. Rev. B* **2016**, *93*, 224510 - 224521.